

Connecting London: The Impact of the Elizabeth Line on Accessibility and Spatial Equity

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Summary

In London, where the majority of employment opportunities are concentrated in the City of London and Canary Wharf, the public transport system plays a key role in connecting people to these jobs. With the opening of the Elizabeth Line in May 2022, parts of East and West London have seen improved travel times to these employment hubs. In this paper, we compare spatial accessibility to employment opportunities before and after this change and assess the spatial equity effects. Using the *r5r* package for *R*, we calculate a gravity-based opportunity metric based on public transport travel times. We subsequently evaluate the spatial equity of changes in job accessibility by profiling areas against socio-economic and socio-demographic characteristics, specifically socio-economic deprivation, share of households with access to a private vehicle, proportion of BAME residents, and unemployment rate structure.

KEYWORDS: public transport accessibility, employment accessibility, GTFS data, spatial equity

1. Background

The City of London employs over 615,000 workers but houses only 8,600 residents (City of London, 2024). This imbalance between where people live and work means that many outer London residents depend on public transport to reach their jobs. Although London is internationally recognised for its extensive and efficient public transport system, access and levels of service vary across neighbourhoods. Where residents in Zones 1-3 can access frequent underground, overground, and bus services, those living further afield are often considerably less well-served. For example, commuters in outer London are twice as likely to rely on cars compared to their more centrally located counterparts (Centre for London, 2023). The opening of the Elizabeth Line in May 2022 significantly improved accessibility along the city's east-west axis, benefiting peripheral labour catchment areas such as Newham and Greenwich. However, this raises important questions about who has benefited most from these improvements, particularly in relation to reducing socio-economic and socio-demographic disparities in access to employment opportunities.

Recent academic research on accessibility to opportunities such as job and public services has focused on evaluating the equity of existing transport systems. Pritchard *et al.* 2019, for instance, analysed the equity of job accessibility by car and public transport in Netherlands' Randstad region, Greater London, and São Paulo. Verduzco Torres and McArthur (2024) developed a range of public transport accessibility indicators to employment opportunities and key services across Great Britain. Other studies have taken scenario-based approaches to model the potential effects of public transport infrastructure investments on job accessibility (Ford *et al.*, 2015). To the best of our knowledge, however, no study has so far explored how the Elizabeth Line has reshaped accessibility patterns and affected job access across the region. This paper therefore sets out to quantify the spatial equity impacts of the Elizabeth Line on job accessibility in Greater London.

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2. Data and methods

To evaluate the impact of the Elizabeth Line on job accessibility in London, we adopt a *ceteris paribus* approach, calculating the number of employment opportunities accessible by public transport based on published public transport timetables, both with and without the Elizabeth Line. Figure 1 summarises the main methodological steps.

Figure 1 Methodology flow diagram illustrating the steps to model the change in job accessibility with the introduction of the Elizabeth Line.

First, travel time estimates are computed using population-weighted centroids of Lower Layer Super Output Areas (LSOAs) as origin and destination points. Following established transport network analysis practices (Bastiaanssen, et al., 2022; Verduzco Torres & McArthur; 2024), a routable walking and public transit network was constructed using OpenStreetMap street network data and public transport timetables. The public transport timetables are sourced from General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) data made available via the Bus Open Data Service (BODS) for buses and underground services, and from the Common Interface File (CIF) format provided by the National Rail Timetable for heavy rail, overground rail, and the Elizabeth Line.

To isolate the impact of the Elizabeth Line, the CIF file was duplicated, and the Elizabeth Line was manually removed from one copy using *Railplan* software. The original and modified CIF files were then exported back into CIF format using the *MoTiON* tool (Transport for London, 2024) and

subsequently converted into GTFS format using the *UK2GTFS* package in R (Morgan, 2020). Travel time estimates were calculated using the *r5r* package (version 2.0.09999) for R (Pereira & Herszenhut, 2023), which builds on *R5*, a multimodal open-source routing engine. This software enables the computation of detailed, door-to-door multimodal routes, incorporating walking and all public transport modes included in the timetables. Using the parameters shown in Table 1, two travel time matrices were created, each containing the travel time from each LSOA to every other LSOA by public transport: one including the Elizabeth Line and one excluding it.

Table 1 Key parameters used in computing the travel time matrixes.

Date of travel	18 September 2024 (Wednesday)
Departure time window	3 hours, from 7 a.m. to 10 am
Travel modes	Walking, public transport*
Maximum travel time allowed	120 minutes, walking distance to egress/access public transport is not limited
Maximum number of transport mode changes	3
Walking speed	5 km/h

* Walking-only routes represent approximately 0.3% of the routes estimated

With the distance matrixes in place, we derived a gravity-based opportunities metric to estimate the number of jobs that can be reached by public transport from each LSOA. Employment figures from the Business Register and Employment Survey were used as a proxy for job opportunities, incorporating both part-time and full-time positions across all industries. The metric further applies a distance decay function based on travel time to account for the diminishing and non-linear value of jobs located further away (Levinson, 1998; El-Geneidy & Levinson, 2006). By holding constant all other factors, namely the origins, destinations, and the rest of the transport network, we then calculated the change in the distribution of accessibility to job opportunities in a scenario with and without the Elizabeth line. In a final step, these changes were assessed by profiling neighbourhoods using selected socio-economic and socio-demographic characteristics: socio-economic deprivation, share of households with access to a private vehicle, proportion of BAME residents, and unemployment rate structure.

3. Results

Figure 2 shows that the Elizabeth Line has significantly expanded access to employment opportunities across Greater London. Before its introduction, job accessibility was highly centralised around Central London; after its introduction, the high-accessibility zones extend to previously underserved neighbourhoods.

Figure 2 Number of travel-time weighted employment opportunities that can be reached within 120 minutes of travel by public transport without (*left*) and with (*right*) the Elizabeth Line.

Figure 3 shows the changes in access to employment opportunities following the introduction of the Elizabeth Line, revealing a substantial increase in accessible jobs in East and West London in particular. Not surprisingly, the largest improvements in accessibility are found near Elizabeth Line stations, but the effects extend well beyond their immediate vicinity. Outer suburban areas such as Newham, Redbridge, and Barking and Dagenham in the east, and Ealing and Hillingdon in the west, which previously faced long commutes and low levels of accessibility, now have significantly improved connections to central employment hubs, with changes in accessibility of up to 500%.

Neighbourhoods in Central London, which were well-connected by public transport even before the Elizabeth Line opened, did not experience significant improvements in job accessibility. Similarly, areas further away, particularly in Southeast and North London, saw little to no improvement in job accessibility. However, as shown in Figure 4, some areas still benefit from a potential reduction in travel time when travelling to the City of London or Canary Wharf in East London.

Figure 3 Percentage change in number of travel-time weighted employment opportunities that can be reached within 120 minutes of travel by public transport after the introduction of the Elizabeth Line.

(a) Canary Wharf

(b) City of London

Figure 4 Reduction in travel time following the introduction of the Elizabeth Line when travelling to the City of London (*left*) and Canary Wharf (*right*).

Figure 5 Distribution of change in time-weighted employment opportunities that can be reached within 120 minutes of travel by decile based on IMD (A), the proportion of BAME residents (B), share of households with access to a private vehicle (C), and the proportion of unemployed residents (D).

To assess the spatial equity effects of changes in access to employment opportunities, we profile neighbourhoods within a 24-minute walking distance catchment area of an Elizabeth Line station, comparing them against socio-economic and socio-demographic characteristics, specifically socio-economic deprivation as measured by the Index of Multiple Deprivation (Figure 5a), the share of the proportion of BAME residents (Figure 5b), the share of households with access to a private vehicle (Figure 5c), and unemployment rate structure (Figure 5d). The figures reveal some differences across socio-economic and socio-demographic groups, although no clear trends emerge. The Palma ratio, the ratio of average accessibility changes for the wealthiest 10% to the average accessibility changes of the poorest 40%, however, increased with 8.91% from 1.01 (without the Elizabeth Line) to 1.10 (with the Elizabeth Line) suggests that more affluent areas have experienced disproportionately higher accessibility gains.

4. Conclusion

Using a before-and-after scenario based on public transport timetables, we show that the Elizabeth Line has substantially improved job accessibility across London. The new transport infrastructure has improved connectivity, particularly along its east-west corridor, linking peripheral labour catchment areas to central employment hubs. While large parts of the region see an increase in accessible jobs, the greatest improvements are concentrated in areas directly served by Elizabeth Line stations. Central London, already well-connected, sees minimal changes, while areas outside the Elizabeth Line corridor, such as Southeast and North London, remain largely disconnected from the improvements. In terms of the distribution of the improvement in job accessibility, benefits appear to be relatively evenly spread across socio-economic and socio-demographic groups, but with no evidence of distributive effects.

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Biographies

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